

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: SPAIN

Water-driven transitional ecosystems: the crucial role of water availability shaping biodiversity and ecosystem functioning

Rebeca Arias-Real¹ & Pilar Hurtado²

¹Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Madrid, Spain.

²Área de Biodiversidad y Conservación, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Móstoles, Spain.

Email: rebeca.arias.real@gmail.com

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14517245>

Most ecosystems on Earth are either consistently covered by water, such as oceans and permanent rivers, or are predominantly dry, such as forests and deserts. However, many ecosystems undergo natural and periodic shifts between wet and dry phases (e.g., intermittent rivers and ephemeral streams, palustrine wetlands, coastal shores, and freeze-thaw lakes). In these water-driven transitional ecosystems, both phases are interconnected components of a single, highly dynamic meta-ecosystem, where biodiversity and ecosystem functionality are shaped by the duration, frequency, and intensity of wet-dry cycles. Despite this inherently coupled dynamic, water-driven transitional ecosystems have historically been studied from a biased perspective, predominantly focusing on their aquatic phase, which currently limits our comprehensive understanding of these unique ecosystems. Addressing this knowledge gap is more important than ever because the number of ecosystems facing wet-dry or dry-wet transitions is increasing globally in response to climate change (e.g., drying lakes and rivers in response to droughts).

Ephemeral river in central Spain (Mediana de Voltoya, Ávila), which remains dry for over 300 days a year.

Biological covers – complex assemblies of organisms such as algae, fungi, bacteria, cyanobacteria, bryophytes, lichens, and protozoa – provide a unique opportunity to assess the response of biodiversity to periodic shifts between wet and dry phases. In fact, biological covers are adapted to wet-dry cycles, developing three-dimensional structures that reflect the interplay between water availability and ecological succession. These communities are

globally distributed and encompass a wide range of forms, from aquatic biofilms found in environments with high water availability, to biocrusts typically associated with environments experiencing water scarcity. Despite their shared organisms, biofilms and biocrusts have often been studied as separate entities, limiting our understanding of how they respond to hydrological change. Recognizing them as part of a continuum underscores their shared eco-evolutionary capacity to adapt to cycles of hydration and desiccation, highlighting their role as a unique component of biodiversity that is essential for advancing our understanding of

Rebeca and Pilar sampling Biological covers.

highly dynamic transitional ecosystems.

In water-driven transitional ecosystems, the temporal availability of water is a core driver of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. Thus, the duration, frequency, and rate of change of wet-dry cycles shape three distinct scenarios that drive the succession and functional contribution of communities with the eco-evolutionary capacity to thrive under fluctuating water availability (i.e., biological covers). Overall, the following scenarios illustrate the interplay of biological cover with wet-dry dynamics, emphasizing how hydrological fluctuations influence biodiversity across biomes from daily to annual cycles:

1. Long and sustained wet transitional phase followed by a short dry phase: This is common in non-perennial marshes and floodplains and may favor water-adapted organisms such as cyanobacteria, protozoa, algae, and bacteria during wet phases. Dry phases allow drying-tolerant lichens and bryophytes to colonize.
2. Repeated alternating cycles of wet and dry phases. This is common in shorelines, which have the potential to host a wide range of biological covers. The maintenance of a certain level of humidity during dry phases supports species such as lichens and bryophytes, whereas wet phases rapidly reactivate cyanobacteria, fungi, and other microorganisms.
3. Short wet transitional phase followed by a prolonged dry phase. This is commonly found in ephemeral streams and may favor the prevalence of biological covers dominated by drying-tolerant lichens and bryophytes, whereas aquatic species rely on their desiccation-resistant traits to survive.

Seasonal dynamics of the intermittent Corneja River (southwest of Avila), a tributary of the Tormes, showcasing its alternating dry and aquatic phases.

Global change disrupts wet-dry cycles, altering the composition, structure, and function of biological cover. These impacts, especially considering the risk of becoming a stable dry ecosystem, pose threats to the contribution of water-driven transitional ecosystems to global biogeochemical cycles, climatic stability, and human welfare, necessitating a more intense investigation of these ecosystems. In addition, extreme wet events (such as floods) can reshape these ecosystems entirely, creating opportunities for new colonization but also challenging ecosystem stability. Understanding water-driven transitional ecosystems as interconnected entities opens up new possibilities for research. We hope that embracing wet-dry-driven transitions will foster a new field of novel interdisciplinary research beyond the current consideration of alternating transitional states as independent and disconnected entities. By embracing these dynamics, we can develop strategies for the conservation and management of these fascinating ecosystems.

Reference

Arias-Real, R., Delgado-Baquerizo, M., Sabater, S., Gutiérrez-Cánovas, C., Valencia, E., Aragón, G., ... & Hurtado, P. (2024). Unfolding the dynamics of ecosystems undergoing alternating wet-dry transitional states. *Ecology Letters*, 27(8), e14488.